

Indonesian Students' Interest on Face to Face and Anonymous- Peer Review in Writing Class

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ABSTRACT

Peer review as a potential pedagogical practice, has gained popularity in university writing classes for ESL/EFL students. The focus in this study is to find out what students prefer to use face-to-face peer review or anonymous peer review. This study uses a survey research approach as a methodology, the data is carried out by distributing questionnaires to students. The participants are students of SMAN 3 Banjarmasin IPA grade 11. The results of the survey data analysis of student interest in the use of face-to-face and anonymous peer techniques 59.4% or 19 students prefer anonymous to face-to-face peer review while 40.6% or 13 students choose face-to-face peer review as the best technique in providing feedback in class writing. This data was obtained from a questionnaire given to 32 people.

INTRODUCTION

Communication becomes a daily activity as a social being in dealing with other people. Especially if our work requires relationships and communication with other people, working in teams, or providing services to other parties such as teachers. This means that communication can be carried out by individuals, groups, to large masses and also the forms of communication are very diverse, and one of the types is through writing or messages conveyed by the communicator.

Writing is a communication tool that is an inseparable part of our daily lives so that in writing there is reciprocal giving as a form of communication. One of the important stages in communicating through writing is giving feedback.

Feedback is a correction on grammar and feedback given by the teacher is needed to improve students' abilities and to improve their writing skills (Ferris, 2006). So that feedback can be one of the media for detailed information provided by teachers to students related to assignments in their learning process (Widarsih & Suherdi, 2019).

Even the incorporation of peer review into a curriculum composition has been popularly practiced in both ESL and EFL contexts 'for its social, cognitive, affective, and methodological benefits' (Rollinson, 2005). And in providing feedback, a commonly known technique is anonymous peer review where Peer review provides learning environments that support the collaborative construction of knowledge (Jonassen & Rohrer-Murphy, 1999), (Kim, 2019)

Despite the potential benefits of peer review, some studies claim that it is less likely to benefit some students. One of the opinions of (Tsui & Ng, 2000) claims that writing comments is generally considered difficult and unpleasant by peer reviewers, both survey L1. It's more efficient to review in face-to-face mode because reviewers can talk about our feedback directly to the author. This is also supported by the assumption that Asian students exhibit difficulty in providing negative feedback because they tend to be hesitant for cultural reasons to criticize others' work and from the results and research (Kim, 2019) which states that the peer-review process must be anonymized, a single-blind mode in which only the writer's name is withheld would be more effective than the double-blind mode employed in the present study.

From this, the researcher is interested in finding out how much interest students in Indonesia have in anonymous and face to face peer review and also wants to identify learning difficulties experienced by students in learning.

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

Method of the study

In this study, researchers used survey research with a quantitative descriptive approach. Survey research design is a quantitative research procedure carried out to obtain a description of the attitudes, behaviors, and characteristics of the population obtained through samples in the population (Creswell, 2012) Furthermore, in descriptive research, there is no treatment for the object under study but describes the circumstances, conditions or events that occur as they are. So that in this study it does not take into account the relationship between the variables. The goal is to use the data we have obtained to solve the problem, rather than to test the hypothesis. This study describes purely the results of the observed objects, then the data obtained are grouped against certain clarifications and then conclusions are drawn. This type was chosen because this study intends to reveal the extent to which students are interested in feedback techniques (face to face or anonymous peer review)..

Time and Location of the Study

This research will be conducted at SMAN 3 Banjarmasin which is located at st. Veteran No.381, Sungai Bilu, East Banjarmasin District which was held for approximately one week, namely May 2022.

Population and Sample of the Study

The population in this study was students of science class 11 SMAN 3 Banjarmasin totaling 32 students. While, for the sample of the study, the sample was taken using the Simple Random Sampling technique, which was taken at random without considering the dominant class or not. The sample used in this study was all students of class 11 science with a total of 32 students.

Procedure of Collecting Data

For data collection using a questionnaire, but beforehand participants will provide comments on the results of their respective writings: First, the teacher provides an explanation or instruction regarding peer review, its method and how it is applied to participants. Then, conditioning participants to sit in pairs, one table consists of two participants. After that, give an explanation of the draft topic that must be written. The topic is about 'favorite things'. And the researcher distributed two blank papers to all participants. The researcher gave instructions to the participants to write paragraphs with the topics that had been discussed. After finishing writing the paragraph, participants were asked to copy the paragraph back on another paper containing two pieces of paper with the names of each participant on it.

After finishing writing paragraphs, participants only collect one book while the rest are held by each. Then instruct participants to exchange their paper with their partner (another participant sitting at the same table). Then participants ask questions on paper containing their partner's paragraphs by writing their names. Papers that have been written are collected for feedback to

researchers. Then participants distribute the second paper, which contains the same paragraph. (Paper is distributed randomly). Meanwhile, the participants again wrote feedback on a second paper containing an anonymous paragraph. Then the participants collect the two. After that, the researcher asked the teacher for help to distribute the questionnaire in the form of a google form link to all participants which they would later fill in the form of a questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter will discover the research result from the data description and the data analysis. This chapter also discuss about the discussion of the test result and the correlation of the result and the theories given in the second chapter.

A. Research Findings

1. Description of Research Implementation

This research was conducted at SMAN 3 Banjarmasin which is located at st. Veteran No.381, Sungai Bilu, East Banjarmasin Regency. The number of respondents was 37 students of science class 11. And for the date of implementation on May 25, 2022 which was carried out in two stages. The first stage, the researcher asked the teacher for help to explain the feedback technique to the students and the students practiced what had been explained. The second stage, the researcher provided a google form link to be distributed to students in which the students filled out a questionnaire that had been prepared by the previous researcher with the help of the teacher in distributing the link to students.

2. Data analysis

a. Language validation linguist validation data

Language validation was carried out to determine the validity of the questionnaire from the language and communication aspects. A linguist is an English lecturer at the English education program at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education at the Muhammad Arsyad Al Banjari Islamic University, Kalimantan, namely Yudha Apriani, M.Pd.

In this stage, special researchers distribute questionnaires via google form to linguists and validation is carried out by linguists using the Guttman Scale which is made in the form of a checklist or gives a value of 1, namely YES with a score of 1 = 20 (if there is no need for revision) and NO with a score of zero (0) = 0 (revision if necessary). After expert validation, improvements are made in accordance with suggestions and comments from linguists. The results of the validation can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. The result of language validity expert

NO	Observed aspects	Score	
		Yes	No
1	Are the words used correctly?	1	-
2	Are the words used clearly legible?	1	-
3	Is the language used easy for students to understand?	1	-
4	Does the writing of the sentence already follow the correct grammatical rules?	1	-
5	Whether the font used does not affect the reading process?	1	-
Score		5	

Based on the scoring table above, it is be able to concluded the questioner is very suitable for use without the need for repair due to get 100 from 5 score.

b. Survey Questionnaire Results Data

Data on student interest in face to face and anonymous, was measured using automatic counting from google form and distributed to 32 students/respondents. And here are the results obtained as follows:

Pie chart 1 Survey percentage results.

The result is from 32 students, there are 19 students choose anonymous peer review with a percentage as 59,4% and 13 students prefer face to face peer review and get 40,6%. For convenience, it can be seen from this bar chart:

Bar chart 1 Comparison of survey results

By looking at the results of this survey, we can conclude that students are more interested in using anonymous peer review in providing feedback.

B. Discussion

The results of the survey data analysis of student interest in the use of face to face and anonymous peer techniques 59,4% or 19 students prefer anonymous over face to face peer review while 40.6% or 13 students choose face to face peer review as the best technique in providing feedback in class writing. This data was obtained from a questionnaire given to 32. So it can be concluded that the students prefer anonymous peer due to several factors, such as:

1. Felling impoliteness gives negative comments

Here are some opinions from the students:

karena jika menggunakan face to face takutnya teman akan merasa tersinggung jadi lebih baik secara anonymous agar teman bisa introspeksi .

If you use face to face, you are afraid that your friends will feel offended, so it's better anonymously so that your friends can introspect.

Kebanyakan orang suka melindungi privasi mereka, saat memberikan komentar/umpan balik, mereka tidak ingin wajah mereka diketahui banyak orang. Oleh sebab itu saya memilih Anonymous Peer Review.

Most people like to protect their privacy, when giving comments/feedback, they don't want their face to be known by many people. That's why I chose Anonymous Peer Review.

Saya takut dibenci oleh orang yang saya kritik. Takut nanti malah menjadi canggung.

I am afraid of being hated by the people I criticize. I'm afraid it will be awkward.

Dalam memberikan sebuah komentar/koreksi sehingga saya tidak memilih nya (anonymous peer review) adalah ketika saya memberikan komentar atau koreksi terhadap teman/orng lain yg memiliki sifat mudah tersinggung, oleh karena itu saya lebih baik jujur secara langsung (dengan catatan harus memakai kata kata yg baik dan tidak menyinggung perasaan teman atau orng lain.) ketimbang harus memakai persamaan kata lain sehingga teman/orng lain tersebut dapat memahami dan mengerti apa yg saya sampaikan.

In providing a comment/correction so that I do not choose it (anonymous peer review) is when I make comments or corrections to friends/other people who have an irritable nature, therefore I better be honest directly (with a note that I must use the words which is good and does not offend friends or other people.) rather than having to use other similar words so that the friend / other person can understand and understand what I have to say.

Karena hal tersebut dapat membuat saya menuliskan hal-hal yang memang perlu dikoreksi, dikomentari dengan jujur tanpa perasaan tidak nyaman karena takut menyakiti perasaan teman/orang lain.

Because it can make me write down things that really need to be corrected, commented honestly without feeling uncomfortable for fear of hurting the feelings of friends/others.

Saya tidak memilih face to face karena akan ada kecenderungan jika para siswa kelas penulis mengenal satu sama lain i.e. komentar/feedback cenderung lebih empatik.

I did not choose face to face because there will be a tendency if the students of the writing class know each other i.e. comments/feedback tend to be more empathic.

2. Privacy

Here is the following statements:

Karena bisa meminimalisir kendala saat yang dikoreksi tidak mengetahui identitas pengoreksi sehingga tidak menimbulkan perpecahan langsung semisal yang dikoreksi tidak menerima atas koreksi tersebut.

Because it can minimize obstacles when the corrected person does not know the identity of the corrector so that it does not cause a direct split, such as the one being corrected does not accept the correction.

3. Commenters feel restricted because their names are written.

Rasa bersalah dan tidak enak hari kalau ada koemntar negatid jadi terpaksa membarikan komentar positif saja.

Feelings of guilt and discomfort if there are negative comments are forced to only give positive comments.

Saya sendiri kurang nyaman akan hal tersebut, karena saya tidak bisa dengan bebas memberikan komentar, memberikan saran, memberikan koreksi dengan jujur karena takut akan menyinggung perasaan teman/orang lain tersebut.

I myself am not comfortable with this, because I cannot freely comment, give suggestions, provide corrections honestly for fear of offending my friends/others.

From the several factors found, respondents feel they prefer to be anonymous because of Asian cultural reasons that express impoliteness in giving negative comments to others (Kim, 2019) and also when giving negative comments on face-to-face feedback they tend to only give a few negative comments. So they feel limited in giving comments because of these factors, then, there is a sense of feeling when giving negative comments because of their privacy.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this chapter, the researcher will provide an explanation of the conclusions, suggestions, and also the limitations of the study.

Conclusion

Based on the results of a survey that has been conducted on the students of SMAN 3 Banjarmasin IPA 11 class, totaling 32 people. It was concluded that they were more interested in using anonymous peer review than face to face peer review. This proves that Asian culture still has a role in the mindset of students who think that giving negative comments directly is considered impolite.

Suggestion

Based on the results of the data analysis, discussion and conclusions, the researcher gives a suggestion that teachers in ESL classes need to provide lessons that focus on developing metalanguage so that students with various L1 backgrounds can voice their views and respond reciprocally to each other in a common language. Likewise for EFL teachers who wish to conduct peer-review sessions in English. Although some students may hesitate or even refuse to express honest opinions, they may be able to overcome their tendencies if they know how to present their opinions in an appropriate manner.

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